

Asymmetric Nonlinearity in the Mechanics of the Mouse Cochlea

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Abstract. Nonlinearity in cochlear mechanics is commonly thought to originate from the mechano-electrical transduction process performed by outer hair cells (OHCs). Nonlinear mechanotransduction introduces compression, suppression, and distortion into the OHC receptor potential, such that these phenomena are evident in the OHC's electromotile response and in vibrations of the organ of Corti as a whole. While it has been suggested that the OHC mechanotransducer function's operating point is centered, so as to produce symmetric receptor currents, maximal gain, and predominantly odd-order distortions, measurements of intracochlear potentials and vibrations from a variety of species and cochlear locations indicate that these currents may be asymmetric, containing significant tonic (i.e., 0 Hz) and even-order distortions. Here, optical coherence tomography was used to evaluate the form of the nonlinearity influencing organ of Corti mechanics at apical, middle, and basal regions of the mouse cochlea. At locations tuned to characteristic frequencies ranging from 9 to 40 kHz, prominent tonic and even-order intermodulation distortions were observed in vibratory responses to single- and two-tone stimuli. The data therefore indicate that the nonlinearity governing OHC responses is fundamentally asymmetric throughout much of the mouse cochlea.

INTRODUCTION

Cochlear hair cells transduce sound-induced displacements of their stereociliary bundles into receptor currents that modulate the transmembrane potential¹. While depolarization of inner hair cells (IHCs) triggers afferent communication with the majority of auditory nerve fibers, the receptor potential of the outer hair cells (OHCs) is thought to primarily drive electromotile force generation²⁻⁴. OHC-generated forces amplify the motions of the surrounding organ of Corti structures and enhance traveling waves as they propagate from base to apex. Nonlinearities in the mechanotransduction process therefore not only shape OHC receptor potentials, but also the motions within the cochlear partition⁵⁻⁶.

The form of the OHC mechanotransducer function, which relates stereociliary bundle deflection to the resulting current, is of interest as it determines the gain provided by OHC electromotility. Typically represented by a first- or second-order Boltzmann function, the OHC mechanotransducer function is often proposed to operate around a point where roughly 50% of the transduction channels are open at rest⁷⁻⁸. This places the operating point near the steepest portion of the function, resulting in the highest gain and maximizing the OHCs' amplifying capability. A consequence of such a centered operating point is that the resulting receptor currents will tend to be more symmetrically depolarizing and hyperpolarizing. They will therefore contain significant odd-order distortion but minimal even-order distortions and tonic (i.e., 0 Hz or 'direct current') components. In contrast, if the operating point is positioned away from the function's center, receptor currents will be more asymmetric, containing tonic, even-order, and odd-order distortions⁹. The relative magnitudes and growth patterns of the distortions measured in cochlear responses therefore provide insight into the form of the mechanotransducer function.

Evidence for significant even-order distortion in cochlear mechanics has been found in auditory nerve responses and cochlear potentials in a variety of species and cochlear locations¹⁰⁻¹³, suggesting that the underlying nonlinearity may, in fact, be asymmetric. Nevertheless, direct observations of asymmetric distortion in basilar membrane vibrations

have been less consistent^{6,13-16}. Fortunately, recent advances in vibrometric techniques such as optical coherence tomography (OCT) have permitted vibration measurements from within or near the OHCs, the presumed source of cochlear distortions. Such measurements have more reliably revealed the presence of even-order harmonics and intermodulation distortion products, as well as tonic components, in OHC region responses from the gerbil cochlear base¹⁷⁻¹⁹ and the mouse cochlear apex²⁰⁻²¹. Here, these findings are extended through vibration measurements at apical, middle, and basal regions of the mouse cochlea, with characteristic frequencies (CFs) ranging from 9 to 40 kHz.

METHODS

Mouse preparation

OCT was used to image and measure sound-evoked vibrations from the intact cochlea in adult (3-7 week old) wild-type CBA/CaJ and C57BL/6J mice. Mice were first deeply anesthetized (80 mg/kg ketamine, 10 mg/kg xylazine) and placed on a heating pad to maintain body temperature at ~38 °C. Supplemental anesthesia was given to maintain areflexia. The skull was exposed and fixed to a custom head-holder with dental cement, and a ventrolateral approach was used to access the left middle ear space. After removing the pinna and resecting a portion of the ear canal, a tube was glued over the exposed eardrum and coupled to the sound delivery system (described below). Upon completion of the desired measurements, mice were euthanized via anesthetic overdose. All procedures were approved by the Institutional Animal Care and Use Committee at the University of Southern California.

OCT imaging and vibrometry

The custom-built OCT system has been described previously²⁰⁻²³. It employs a swept light source (Insight Photonic Solutions, Inc.; Lafayette, CO) with a 1,310 nm center wavelength and 95 nm bandwidth, and achieves axial and lateral imaging resolutions of 12.5 and 9.8 μm (full width at half maximum), respectively.

After opening the middle ear space, the light source was scanned across the cochlear bone to obtain cross-sectional images. Sound-evoked displacements of individual points in the images were then obtained. Measurements were primarily taken from the center of the organ of Corti, presumably near the junction between the OHCs and the underlying Deiters' cells (DCs), at cochlear locations with CFs of approximately 9, 20, or 40 kHz. The vibrometry sampling rate was 100 kHz, allowing measurement of vibrations at frequencies up to 50 kHz.

Stimulus paradigms

Vibratory responses were obtained for single- or two-tone stimuli, which were delivered to the eardrum via tubing coupled to either a Fostex speaker (FT17H; Fostex, Tokyo, Japan) or an otoacoustic emission probe (ER-10X; Etymotic Research, Elk Grove Village, IL). The Fostex speaker had a superior high-frequency output and was therefore used in measurements from the 20 and 40 kHz locations. The speaker was removed from its housing so that a speculum tip could be glued over the diaphragm, allowing it to be easily connected to the sound delivery tube. Stimuli presented with the Fostex speaker were calibrated before each experiment using the pressure measured by an 1/8" microphone (Type 4138-A; Brüel & Kjær, Virum, Denmark) inserted into the end of the sound delivery tube. When using the ER-10X probe, stimuli were calibrated *in situ* using the pressure measured by the probe microphone. Similar vibrations have been measured from the 9 kHz location using either method.

Most measurements were obtained using ~100 ms tones presented once every 110 ms, with responses averaged over 4-32 stimulus presentations. However, for measurements examined in the time domain, responses were obtained using 7 ms tones presented once every 20 ms and averaged over 1,000 to 4,000 presentations. Acoustic and postmortem measurements confirmed that any distortion observed *in vivo* was cochlear in origin.

RESULTS

Broadband nonlinearity is observed in organ of Corti vibrations at all cochlear locations

A representative OCT image of a CBA/CaJ mouse cochlea is shown in Fig. 1a, highlighting the three locations where vibrations were measured. While the mechanics of the apical, 9 kHz location have been extensively studied²⁰⁻²³, measurements from the 20 and 40 kHz locations obtained through the intact cochlear bone have not yet been described in detail. This is primarily because of the limited amount of light returning from these deeper regions, which reduces both the image quality and the signal-to-noise ratio of the vibration measurements. Nevertheless, it has been possible to obtain interpretable responses from both mid-cochlear and basal locations that exhibit all the characteristics of nonlinear, cochlear amplification.

As shown in Fig. 1b, vibratory responses to single tones measured from roughly the center of the organ of Corti at each location revealed a similar degree of level- and frequency-dependent nonlinearity. Displacements are shown normalized to the evoking stimulus pressure (i.e., as a “gain” relative to the stimulus), thus highlighting the nonlinearity in the responses. At all locations, responses to CF tones presented at 30 dB SPL tones exhibited ~50 dB more gain than those for 90 dB SPL tones. The nonlinearity diminished with decreasing frequency but could still be observed at least two octaves below the CF. Broadband nonlinearity is a consistent characteristic of OHC region vibrations^{17-18,24}, providing some confidence that the measurements from the ~20 and 40 kHz regions were from the OHCs or nearby supporting cells. Note that while data from each location are from different individual mice, the CF-dependent variations in response magnitude and tuning evident in Fig. 1b have been consistently observed across multiple mice.

FIGURE 1. (a) OCT image of a CBA/CaJ mouse cochlea. Highlighted are the three locations where vibrations were examined. (b) Magnitudes and phases of vibratory responses to single tones at each location in three different mice. Each measurement was made from a point near the center of the organ of Corti (see magenta arrows in (a) for the approximate positions). Displacement magnitudes are normalized to the evoking stimulus pressure and plotted for stimulus levels of 30 to 90 dB SPL in 10 dB steps, with responses for the lowest and highest stimulus levels indicated. Phase curves for all stimulus levels largely overlap at the scale shown. Data for the 9 and 44 kHz locations are from CBA/CaJ mice, while data for the 22 kHz location are from a C57BL/6J mouse.

Tonic displacements are observed throughout the mouse cochlea

At the 9 kHz location, sound elicits tonic displacements of the OHC-DC junction and reticular lamina that are consistent with tonic OHC contraction, with the OHC-DC junction moving toward scala vestibuli and the reticular lamina moving toward scala tympani²⁰ (e.g., Fig. 2a). Similar tonic displacements have recently been observed in the gerbil cochlear base^{17,19}.

As shown in Fig. 2b-d, tonic OHC region displacements are also found at middle and basal regions of the mouse cochlea. Waveforms of responses to near-CF tones measured from near the center of the organ of Corti at the 20 and 40 kHz locations were asymmetric and exhibited tonic displacements toward scala vestibuli. When sufficiently reflective points were present at the top of the organ of Corti, tonic displacements measured from these points were

typically in the opposite direction, toward scala tympani (not shown). As in the apex, tonic displacements could exceed the cycle-by-cycle response at the stimulus frequency. This is particularly evident in the response to the 40 kHz, 70 dB SPL tone (Fig. 2d), for which the tonic response was twice as large as the response at the stimulus frequency. At the ~40 kHz location, responses to near-CF tones often decreased as the stimulus level increased above 60 dB SPL (Fig. 2c-d), reminiscent of the “hyper-compression” observed for OHC region responses in the gerbil base²⁴.

FIGURE 2. (a)-(d) Displacement waveforms for near-CF tones measured from the 9 kHz (a), 22 kHz (b), and 42 kHz (c-d) locations. Responses were obtained from the center of the organ of Corti at each location. Thick gray lines are the low-pass-filtered versions of the waveforms, revealing tonic displacements toward scala vestibuli. Data from (a) and (b) are from CBA/CaJ and C57BL/6J mice, respectively. Data from (c)-(d) are from an individual CBA/CaJ mouse but at two stimulus levels. Note that different magnitude scales are used for responses from each cochlear location.

Even-order intermodulation distortion is also observed at each cochlear location

OHC region responses in the mouse cochlear apex and gerbil cochlear base have previously been shown to contain significant harmonic distortions, including both even-order (e.g., 2nd and 4th) and odd-order (e.g., 3rd and 5th) harmonics¹⁹⁻²⁰. At the 20 and 40 kHz locations, spectra of single-tone responses often contained evidence of 2nd and 3rd harmonics, though many of these components were aliased by the 100 kHz sampling rate. Additionally, assuming these harmonics are produced by the electromotile response to distortions introduced by mechanotransduction, they are presumably strongly attenuated by low-pass filtering of the OHC receptor potential^{17,25} and possibly further limited by the kinetics of electromotility²⁶. Thus, for simplicity, even- and odd-order distortions were characterized here using responses to two tones (at frequencies f_1 and f_2 , with $f_2 > f_1$), as has recently been done at the 9 kHz location²¹ (e.g., Fig. 3a).

As shown in Fig. 3b-c, spectra of two-tone responses measured from the center of the organ of Corti at the 20 and 40 kHz locations also contained numerous intermodulation distortion products. These included the even-order “quadratic” difference tone ($f_2 - f_1$), which was often most prominent for low-to-moderate stimulus levels, and the more commonly measured odd-order “cubic” difference tone ($2f_1 - f_2$; note, however, that this component barely exceeds the noise floor in Fig. 3c). Growth patterns of $f_2 - f_1$ and $2f_1 - f_2$ were highly similar across cochlear locations when the f_2 tone was presented at 60 dB SPL and the f_1 tone was varied in level (Fig. 3d-f). Though the levels of the distortions relative to the responses at f_1 and f_2 varied widely between measurements, it remains to be determined whether this level relationship varies consistently with cochlear location.

DISCUSSION

The observation of tonic components and even-order intermodulation distortions in apical and basal regions indicates that the nonlinearity influencing OHC responses is asymmetric throughout much of the mouse cochlea. If the nonlinearity is attributed to mechanotransduction, this suggests that the OHC stereociliary bundle rests at a position where fewer than 50% of the channels are open at rest, such that bundle deflection produces receptor currents that are asymmetrically depolarizing. While this implies that the gain provided by the OHCs may be sub-optimal, the bias of the operating point away from the center of the mechanotransducer function need not be extreme. Modeling of OHC region responses from the 9 kHz location reveals that the level-dependent growth of the tonic, harmonic, and intermodulation distortions can all be replicated using a first-order Boltzmann function with ~33% of the current activated at rest²⁰⁻²¹.

FIGURE 3. (a)-(c) Spectra of organ of Corti displacement responses to two-tone stimuli, with f_2 set to near the CF of each measurement location and $f_2/f_1 = 1.17$. Both stimulus tones were presented at levels (L_1 and L_2) of 60 dB SPL. Data in (a) and (c) are from different CBA/CaJ mice, and data in (b) are from a C57BL/6J mouse. Response peaks at the stimulus frequencies and relevant DP frequencies are labeled. (d)-(e) Growth of two-tone response components for the same measurement locations and mice as shown in (a)-(c). L_2 was fixed at 60 dB SPL while L_1 was varied. Dashed lines indicate linear growth.

Though an asymmetric transducer function is necessary to produce tonic and quadratic distortions, note that the prominence of these components is owed in part to the low-pass characteristic of OHC region vibrations^{17,20,27}. At the 9 kHz location, for example, OHC region displacements appear to be reduced by ~ 6 dB/octave for frequencies above ~ 1.75 kHz²⁰. Low-pass filtering is necessary to produce tonic components that are larger than the cycle-by-cycle responses, and, under the two-tone stimulus paradigm used here, would more strongly attenuate responses at f_1 , f_2 , and $2f_1 - f_2$ compared to at $f_2 - f_1$, which falls closer to the filter corner frequency. While it is convenient to attribute the experimentally observed low-pass characteristic to membrane filtering of the OHC receptor potential, other sources of mechanical and/or electrical filtering may also shape the responses. Differences in the magnitudes of the intermodulation distortions relative to the stimulus responses observed across cochlear location in Fig. 3 could result from variations in the OHC membrane corner frequency^{8,17} or simply from the selection of measurement points with different mechanical properties. Comprehensive data on the frequency responses across the organ of Corti's width at each location are needed to assess these possibilities.

Since the present report focused on responses to near-CF tones, it remains to be determined if the form of the nonlinearity underlying OHC responses in the mouse cochlea depends on stimulus frequency and/or level. Indeed, the degree and polarity of the asymmetry in OHC receptor potentials in the base and apex of the guinea pig appears to be a complex function of the stimulus level, frequency, and cochlear location^{7,12}. In the gerbil cochlear base, level-dependent polarity reversals in the tonic component of OHC region displacements have recently been described²⁷. Whether the underlying nonlinearity dynamically changes its form in response to sound under natural listening conditions is an intriguing possibility that also needs to be explored.

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COMMENTS AND DISCUSSION

[Jont Allen]: So there's a magic number in your data that you didn't explain, and that is 60 dB. And I found that magic number too. So when you bring up a low-frequency suppressor, when it gets to 60 dB, the suppression kicks in (that's based on neural data that I measured), and that's where the suppressor crosses the excitation threshold. I just want to verify that you agree with the observation that you get suppression when the suppressor starts to become excitatory in the tail region.

[James Dewey]: So the cross-over [where the suppressor starts to reduce the probe response and dominate the total response] being 60 dB is true when the level of the probe tone is 60 dB. But whenever the probe tone is lower in level, you get suppression when the suppressor level is lower than 60 dB. 60 dB was just a good number for being able to show more data above the noise floor. [To clarify further, 60 dB does not appear to be a magic number in any of the mechanical data I've measured. Some work needs to be done to better relate these previous auditory nerve suppression data to what is happening in the mechanics.]

[Wei Dong]: The broadly distributed nonlinearity at the 20 and 40 kHz locations appears to be exhibited only at 90 dB SPL, which seems different from other studies in gerbils (e.g., Fig. 6b in Cooper et al., 2018). Do you think this difference could be due to species variation?

[James Dewey]: The degree of broadband nonlinearity observed could indeed be a complex function of species, cochlear location, and the exact measurement point chosen. However, another important consideration is the use of multi-tone stimuli in many of the gerbil measurements (as in Cooper et al., 2018), which will increase the overall sound pressure and amount of OHC stimulation for a nominal stimulus level.

[Samiya Alkhairy]: The premise is that if the mechanotransduction function nonlinearity is asymmetric, then this will result in tonic and even-order distortions. Could you explain this or illustrate it using a simple derivation? I presume the premise can only be derived using a direct system in which you consider the output given an input into some symmetric or asymmetric nonlinear mechanotransduction function. However, building on the premise, you take the observations of tonic and even-order distortions of recorded motion to mean an asymmetry in the mechanotransduction function of the OHC. I'm confused as to why this is valid as the recorded motion is a result of a closed-loop system of which the mechanotransduction is only a component as opposed to a direct set of measurements of the mechanotransduction function. Even if one considers a forward model with a mechanotransduction function as part of the entire cochlear system, I would imagine that the resultant nonlinearity of the system differs in some ways from that of the mechanotransduction function.

[James Dewey]: Thank you for the comments. The dependence of even- and odd-order distortions on the symmetry of the nonlinearity has been described in detail elsewhere, and I now cite a review article that discusses the general concept [ref. 9]. It is true that there are many nonlinear elements at play in the active cochlea, and these can all influence the measured vibrations. However, the mechanotransducer function is commonly thought to be the dominant source of nonlinearity that gives rise to distortion products and related phenomena. It is also straightforward to replicate many of the nonlinearities in OHC region motion using a single, first-order Boltzmann function (see refs. [20-21]). Thus, invoking multiple nonlinearities is not required to explain the data. That said, I do not claim to be measuring the mechanotransducer function. In the Discussion, I also include the qualification, "If the nonlinearity is attributed to mechanotransduction...". If the observed nonlinearity was dominated by something other than mechanotransduction, this would certainly be an interesting finding and would necessitate the re-interpretation of a wide variety of cochlear measurements.